

**Mapping Affective Geographies of the
Indian Subcontinent: A Textual Materialist
Reading of Pritika Chowdhry's Partition
Anti-Memorial Project (2007-22)**

Sneha Roy

Introduction

One of the foremost objectives of feminist political geography includes the exposure of the violence inherent in the making of political boundaries, the repercussions of which are often, undeniably gendered. While cartography thus assumes the high role of being an objective, scientifically grounded practice that provides a visual, two-dimensional relief of spatial terrain, the interrogation of the dominant discourses that majorly influence the cartographic process hardly finds a mention in everyday conversations. Of late, however, there has been a surge in appropriating the cartographic

practice in artistic and literary works to pose questions and subvert the authority of maps, both political and local, imagining newer ways of configuring and occupying space. In the world of art especially, there is no shortage of artists who have continued to be inspired especially by the politics of aesthetics and visual artistry that goes into map-making, and who experiment and thwart its assumed objectivity by several means and ways of revealing its textuality. From using the map itself as a material to transforming geographic data into visual art, what catches one's attention is the number of artists who make a wide range of socio-political statements through their experimental encounters with the practice of cartography. Surveying the contemporary global scene, maps as aesthetic and socio-political objects have permeated the consciousness of global artists in myriad ways. They use maps to explore themes of migration, displacement, and other geopolitical issues such as refugee crisis, as seen in Mona Hatoum's *Present Tense* (1996), Julie Mehretu's *Black City* (2007) and Tiffany Chung's *Reconstructing an Exodus History* (2020); critique state militarism and new forms of imperialism, exemplified by Joyce Kozloff's *Targets* (2000); engage in art-based activism for environmental causes and highlighting subjective biases inherent in map-making, such as Maya Lin's *52 Ways to See the Earth* (2008), and endorse social justice issues through collaborative art-based criticism as visible from Liz Mogel's *An Atlas of Radical Cartography* (2007). Closer to home, Pritika Chowdhry's *Partition Anti-Me-*

morial Project (2007-22) of the Partition of India catches one's attention, which attempts a radical mapping of the affective geography of the Indian subcontinent by emphasising the textuality of the political map, which thus opens it to interrogation, and activates possible routes of subversion. Highlighting the gendered violence that the Partition wrought, Chowdhry's work stands out for its use of experimental cartography as a means of healing and recuperation for the aggrieved. One of the major critical lenses one can use to put into relief the politics of Chowdhry's experimentations with the cartographic text is that of textual materialism, which in Bill Brown's words, is "...a mode of analytic objectification that focusses on the physical properties of an embodied text" (2010,25). As a method of critical analysis, textual materialism then reveals to us how the very constituent physical elements that create the very sensorial, embodied experience of the "text" as we access it, has a lot to reveal as well about the socio-cultural signifying systems that the text is a part of. Undertaking a reading of the exhibition in that strain, one sees that Chowdhry accomplishes her objectives in two ways: First, by the employment of intertextuality through the citation of South Asian literary works activating and making visible unexpected circuits of meaning-making; second, by utilising the map itself as a substrate along with the use or allusion to other corporeal, bodily objects or extensions such as skin, hair, pig guts and fabric, on which she plays out different counter-geographies of confronting

spatiality. This paper argues that in thus highlighting the textuality of the map using a materialist approach, Chowdhry carves an affective feminist geography which does away with the notion of the map as an intellectual “closed” textual product of the mind alone, subverting its monopoly of assumed governance and regulation of our bodies in space.

Outlining the most important rules in the cartographic process, J.B Harley in his famous article, “Deconstructing the Map” comments on the stress upon scientific rigour in producing a real and objective account of space, which assumes that the reality of objects in the real world “can be expressed in mathematical term; that systematic observation and measurement offer the only route to cartographic truth; and that this truth can be independently verified” (1989, 4). Such an emphasis on scientific neutrality and objectivity as channelled by those in positions of power to regulate space and how people navigate space have been important factors in ascribing a certain sense of sanctity and authority to the map, fortifying it beyond interrogation and distortion. Harley states that to demystify and de-neutralise the concept of the map, it is required that one approaches the map as a cartographic text, that is as a cultural product, instead of thinking of it as a mirror of nature, thus accepting its textuality, and opening it further to several interpretative possibilities. Approaching it as a text, Harley then demonstrates how employing deconstruction as a

method leads to important discoveries in understanding and decoding a specific intentionality and relationality, especially the influence of power-based social relations, in the map-making process. Exposing how science itself assumed the function of a metaphor in post-Enlightenment maps, Harley writes:

Cartography inscribes this cultural model upon the paper and we can examine it in many scales and types of maps. Precision of instrument and technique merely serves to reinforce the image, with its encrustation of myth, as a selective perspective on the world. Thus maps of local estates in the European ancient regime, though derived from instrumental survey, were a metaphor for a social structure based on landed property...Maps of the European states, though constructed along arcs of the meridian, served still as a symbolic shorthand for a complex of nationalist ideas. And world maps, though increasingly drawn on mathematically defined projections, nevertheless gave a spiralling twist to the manifest destiny of European overseas conquest and colonization. In each of these examples we can trace the contours of metaphor in a scientific map. This in turn enhances our understanding of how the text works as an instrument operating on social reality. (1989, 10)

While Harley resorted to deconstruction to reflect upon the textuality of cartographic texts or maps by reading between the lines literally and figuratively to come to

important derivations from the tangentially apparent, the question that arises is how does one extract from such textuality what one finds amiss or what the text has intentionally been configured to eliminate? Among the many artists and writers who appropriated the cartographic text in several creative forms to impinge the same with their rhetoric, Pritika Chowdhry's installations which are a part of the *Partition Anti-Memorial Project* (2007-22) stand out for their simultaneous employment of the map as both metaphor and substrate, thus carving affective geographies of the Indian Subcontinent, with respect to the Partition. In focusing on the embodied and the affective, Chowdhry's work is thus more in line with what is outlined as the other major way of approaching maps which highlights the embodied, experiential nature of mapping practices. Emphasising its dynamic state of becoming, here one learns to approach "maps as not unified representations but as constellations, as ongoing processes" (Kitchin 2009, 16). Now while Jacque Micieli-Voutsinas in his paper titled "Subaltern" Remembrances: Mapping Affective Approaches to Partition Memory" (2013), examines Chowdhry's exhibition to study subaltern memory-production engaging affect theory and subaltern studies as a framework, what remains to be examined is the politics of Chowdhry's artistic method, specifically the minute details and elements that materially and textually provide the exhibitions with its internal rhetoric. That is, while Chowdhry follows in the footsteps of Kitchin et. al

(2009) in emphasising the textuality of the map to puncture its fixity, she exposes the map's "state of becoming", its processual nature with a materially embodied twist, while consequently highlighting its latent dynamic, unstable and fluid qualities. Out of the ten experiential art installations that make up *The Partition Anti-Memorial Project* engaging with the geopolitics of South Asia from a counter-memory perspective, this paper takes a closer look at three specific installations to advance and situate the textual materialist strain that makes up for a significant part of the logic and rhetoric of these installations, namely *Cracking India* (2022), *Remembering the Crooked Line* (2009-10) and *The Masters' Tongues* (2009) which majorly address cartographic practice and textual realities of colonisation and decolonisation.

The Politics of Nomenclature and Cartography

Before moving on to closely reading the installations which make up the crux of this paper, what also requires one's attention is the obvious and the apparent: Chowdhry's strategic nomenclature of these select installations which firmly places them in a complex constellation of intertextuality. The art installation memorialising the historic Radcliffe Line, a boundary arbitrarily drawn in the year 1947 by Sir Cyril Radcliffe dividing India and Pakistan which led to horrific consequences on both sides of the border, is named by Chowdhry *Cracking India: The Line That Still Bleeds* (2022). The phrase

"Cracking India" is borrowed from Bapsi Sidhwa's 1988 novel titled *Cracking India* which traces the journey of a young girl witnessing the Partition, and provides an intimate portrait of the gendered havoc it wreaks on those around her. Similarly, the installation *Remembering the Crooked Line: The Skin of the Nation* (2009-10) is also strategically titled, which features an intensive, creative critique of maps and cartography as tools and technologies of colonisation and nation-building, memorialising specifically the partitions of the Indian subcontinent in the 20th century. As a project which puts together in a comparative framework the many partitions of the 20th century, the title of the exhibition aptly derives its inspiration from the feminist writer Ismat Chughtai's 1967 novel titled *Terhi Lakeer* (*The Crooked Line*) published in the aftermath of the Partition of India, which too is a coming-of-age novel of sorts of a Muslim woman in India. This conscious juxtaposition of political maps to fictional literary works narrativising the Partition strengthens the application of the textual metaphor to the cartographic text that Chowdhry aims to build up through the project. Through the practice of such citation, Chowdhry trains the audience to trace the complex network in which the cartographic text locates itself, in the process what becomes visible are the hitherto unexpected but latent circuits of meaning-production and circulation for cartographic knowledge.

Figure 1. “Radcliffe Line West”Cracking India.
©Pritika Chowdhry, 2022

One can illustrate the same by taking the example of the Cracking India installations, which through their material, three-dimensional manifestations of the Radcliffe Line emphasise the material, physical violence of what otherwise seems like a one-dimensional arbitrary boundary dividing the two countries (Fig.1). This affective, embodied dimension is further underscored by the invocation of Sidhwa’s novel which provides an intimate, sensitive access to the horrors the Partition unleashed, especially on the women. A particular scene from the

novel, the one in which the girl-protagonist Lenny ruminates on the logic and material possibility of a Partition, is specifically helpful in comprehending the fullest potential of Chowdhry's use of intertextuality as a tool:

India is going to be broken. Can one break a country?
And what happens if they break it where our house
is? Or crack it further up on Warris Road? How will
I ever get to Godmother's then? (Sidhwa 1988, 54)

Chowdhry's art installation is thus the physically-manifest response to Lenny's thoughts, which in furthering the dimensionality of the Radcliffe Line provides visual cues to the rounded, material historical consequences of what otherwise appears to be a harmless, flat line on a page. The installation thus locates itself in the gap between the seemingly flat and harmless surface-level visuality of the cartographic text on the page and the overwhelming gendered experience of navigating space in real life, especially spaces partitioned and visited with brute violence in the wake of the partitioning. It also gestures at the material power of such textuality, whose effects do not remain limited to the medium on which it is inscribed. What is also important to be noticed is the type and nature of texts that Chowdhry draws reference to in pinning down certain important landmarks in the complex web of intertextuality in which every text locates itself. In consciously choosing fictional texts written by South Asian women, Chowdhry ensures that the

titles function as signposts, as landmarks, for initiating the audience into newer visual regimes around map-reading. The heralding in of newer, visual regimes around map-reading is important in ensuring that the change is not only at the level of the text itself but also in the socio-cultural network it locates itself in. Through the invocation of fictional texts for the naming of a cartographic text, she aims at the dissolution of the assumed hierarchisation of different texts, with cartographic texts assumed to be objective and scientific occupying a higher position of power over literary texts whose locus of influence is “merely cultural” and subjective in nature. Thus, through the politics of allusion-citation, the cartographic text and its “open-ended”, dynamic and fluid nature are stressed, its malleable nature underscored further by the increase in dimensions. Now, while maps as cartographic intertexts have been well-discussed by both schools of critical cartography, deconstructive and embodied, the notion of “processual intertextuality” developed by David Cooper and Gary Priestnall (2011) helps further understand the gendered connotations of the exhibition’s intertextual nature. Through processual intertextuality, one approaches maps and mapping practices as “systems of cultural signification which are inextricably embedded within the material world and which are brought-into-being with each embodied reading and use” (Cooper and Priestnall 2011, 250). This aspect of embodiment in a material world finds artistic visualisation in Chowdhry’s gendering of the Radcliffe Line

through her appropriation of the colour pink which she uses to memorialise the gendered violence of the Partition and evoke subjective memories through the invocation of Sidhwa's 1988 novel which acts as an intimate witness to the horrors unleashed on women's lives. Similarly, recolouring the Radcliffe Line as pink, Chowdhry also attempts to rewrite such texts in an unconventional vein, where for once the substrate is not the body of a woman but the cartographic text itself. Here then the substrate signals towards symbolic access to an empowered textual condition through readerly access and engagement with the text, and an exit from the conventional tropes in artistic and literary work of treating the gendered body as the only available path to agency, signalling newer trajectories.

Figure 2. Remembering the Crooked Line.
©Pritika Chowdhry, 2009-10

Embodiment, Material Referentiality, and Cartography

How then this processual intertextuality is assembled, materially configured and “comes into being” plays an important role in understanding the aspect of embodiment which is the most important rhetoric that Chowdhry (2009-10) instils into the cartographic text. *Remembering the Crooked Line: The Skin of the Nation Anti-Memorial Project* is an “intensive investigation of maps and cartography as technologies of colonisation and border-making, nation-building, and ethnic divisions” (“Remembering the Crooked Line”) (Fig.2). It is a sculptural installation in six parts, titled “Girls playing Ringa Ringa Roses”, “Women playing Ringa Ringa Roses”, “Kite flying”, “Game of Parchisi/ Parcheesi”, “Game of Chess”, and “Soundscape”. The very conscious selection of materials used to make and assemble these installations is important in undertaking a close reading of these select pieces which deal specifically with cartography. As Chowdhry’s webpage dedicated to the installation enlists, the following materials have been used for “engag[ing] the viewers in a visceral way”: Raw silk, Khaddar cotton dyed with tea, dupioni silk, handmade paper, hair, thread, turmeric, surgical sutures, and pig guts (“Remembering the Crooked Line”). Chowdhry mentions “material referentiality” as an approach to address the question of Chowdhry’s choice of material, through the reference to Christina Mills’ work on materiality:

The artwork's physicality, those aspects that can be sensed and verified by viewers, is a first consideration; physicality impacts content and, subsequently, meaning...Another aspect of materiality as a theory is that art locates viewers within their corporeal selves by engaging the senses; such experiences are, naturally, unique and individual to each viewer. (2009, 1)

The importance of material referentiality seamlessly ties into the operations of processual intertextuality as well, through which one understands better how an embodied reading of the installation takes place. Going deeper into the role that the cartographic text plays in this specific installation which attempts an affective critique of the cartographic process, we need to examine the unexpected ways in which Chowdhry employs the map in these specific installations.

Figure 3. Ringa- Ringa- Roses I. Part of Remembering the Crooked Line ©Pritika Chowdhry, 2009-10

Figure 4. Ringa-Ringa-Roses II. Part of Remembering the Crooked Line©Pritika Chowdhry, 2009-10

In both the installations, “Girls Playing Ringa Ringa Roses” and “Women Playing Ringa Roses”, one sees ethnic shirts around an imaginary circle suspended in the air, playing the popular game (Fig. 3 and 4). These shirts, interestingly made of raw silk, have map lines weaved into them with hair felted onto the surface to create the visual feel of a newly carved border between two partitioned countries. This reconfiguration of the map, changing its functionality to that of a fabric over a phantom body, inscribing a border onto its surface with a bodily extension such as hair, carves a sensuous, tactile geography on the

textual surface, which accomplishes the aim of achieving a “skin-like” effect as the artist intended. This effect is not simply experienced through touch, it is achieved through vision and affect as well; and the underlying logic is best understood if one revisits Sean Cubitt’s theorisation of “The Materiality of The Text” (1998), an out-take digitally archived from his work on *Digital Aesthetics*, which provides us important directions for tracking the many ways in which a text occupies material shape and achieves circulation through networks of intertextuality. A specific paragraph is of particular importance:

Texts long for materiality, but because they can never wholly and integrally inhabit an actual edition, they are no sooner embodied than they begin to disintegrate. No single edition of a text will ever exhaust the variations of which the text is formed. A certain scholarly mode of reading is an attempt to see through the material of the book to find the ideal text beyond it: a practice which takes as its premise that the text and its actually existing variants are not the same, and which tries, in a spirit of piety, to fix the unfeasible. (Cubitt 1998)

These lines find a newer meaning when seen from the perspective of these two installations by Chowdhry who strategically pins down the materiality of the cartographic text to that of a fabric covering a three-dimensional, bodily persona caught mid-air and mid-action. The materiality it acquires thus is very much in touch,

literally and figuratively with the aspect of embodiment, literally covering an imaginary body suspended in the air. Interestingly, even as it inhabits its current state, it cannot attain the state of complete occupation due to its “hollowed-out internal condition” covering a phantom being, thus implying that the search for an “ideal text” will always be incomplete as there exists no cartographic text yet which does not in any way resort to or lead to violence in its actual materialisation. Also, in wrapping the cartographic text around a phantom body in this manner, Chowdhry emphasises the violence of the “textual condition” (McGann 1991) with respect to how a Eurocentric and patriarchal hold on textuality affects and disrupts one’s normal state of being and occupying space, more so for women and other minority groups. The same is shown to manifest and express itself visually and affectively on the “skin-like” surface of the cartographic text which is ruptured and wounded. While Micieli (2013) invokes the work of the sociologist Avery Gordon (1997) for locating his examination of affect and subaltern memory in Chowdhry’s exhibition, a transplantation of the same reference here generates newer meaning concerning the context and argument of the paper. Micieli quotes Gordon to illustrate how “[b]eing haunted draws us affectively, sometimes against our will and always a bit magically, into a structure of feeling of a reality we come to experience, not as cold knowledge, but as a transformative recognition...To write ghost stories implies that ghosts are real, that is to say, that they produce material *affects*.” (Gordon quoted

in Micieli 2013, 40). What is illuminating is in executing a textual materialist reading of the exhibition, the production of “material affect” literally exposes itself as the aim of Chowdhry’s installations, where in evoking a textuality that feels like skin to the touch, one is reminded of the inextricable link that binds the human world to textuality, thus alerting us to the need to take into consideration the material consequences of seemingly non-consequential acts of textual engagement. This binding human connection to the realm of textuality reminds one of McGann’s attempts at theorising the study of “materialist hermeneutics” in his introduction to the book *The Textual Condition* where it “considers texts as autopoietic mechanisms operating as self-generating feedback systems that cannot be separated from those who manipulate and use them” (1991,18).

Figure 5. The Shadow Lines 1. Part of Remembering the Crooked Line.©Pritika Chowdhry, 2009-10

Figure 6. The Crooked Lines (on the top) and Figure 7. Lines of Control (on the bottom). Part of Remembering the Crooked Line. ©Pritika Chowdhry, 2009-10

Playing with the Cartographic Text

This inseparability is stressed through how Chowdhry ensures that cartographic relics become a part of every-

thing human beings are engaged and connected with, making sure that its imprint also does not leave out moments of leisure, play and pleasure— moments one believes to be transcendental and beyond the machinations of such politics, as is visible in the installations titled “Kite-Flying”, “Game of Parcheesi” and “Game of Chess” (Fig 5,6 and 7 respectively) . If in “Kite-Flying”, handmade kites onto which maps of partitioned countries of the twentieth century have been drawn, burnt and sewn onto its surface, are then hung from the ceiling, “Game of Parcheesi” and “Game of Chess” feature life-like game sets on which maps featuring partitioned countries have been sewn onto the surface. Floor cushions have been laid out inviting the viewer to come take a shot at the game. In doing so, there surfaces a double logic that further emphasises and punctures the authority of the cartographic text as a closed text - on the one hand, it exposes the casual sleight of hand and cold cruelty with which countries are partitioned by the dominant and the powerful treating the cartographic text with a sense of casualty and playfulness, and on the other hand, it also provides the aggrieved common people to transgress and play beyond the boundaries of the partitioned countries, a momentary act of agency and subversion simulated by playing with what should have been a symbolic text demanding obeisance and loyalty. Here Chowdhry directs its viewers towards a newer way of reading the map, one in which acknowledging its textuality also provides a gateway for agency and empowerment, if not in any other sense, at least in the symbolic

realm of making meaning and experience. One recalls Barthes' notion of "play" as invoked for defining a text in comparison to what we know as a piece of "work":

In fact, reading, in the sense of consuming, is not playing with the text. "Playing" must be taken here in all the polysemy of the term: the text itself "plays" (like a door that "plays" back and forth on its hinges; like a fishing rod in which there is some "play"); and the reader plays twice over: he plays at the Text (ludic meaning), he seeks a practice which reproduces it; but, so that this practice is not reduced to a passive, interior mimesis (the Text being precisely what resists this reduction), he plays the Text." (Barthes 1977, 62)

In thus juxtaposing and superimposing the cartographic text onto the surface of game boards, the installation underscores the rhetoric of subverting the authority and grip that a cartographic text exercises in one's daily life, by providing the viewer with an outlet to be the one handling his or her fate for once; while for those holding power, it is both an exposure and a refusal at the same time to not comply with their authority or live in a state of passivity. This paradoxical nature of cartographic textuality is then analogous to the paradoxical relationship that women share with spatiality, as Gillian Rose, a prominent feminist geographer theorises in her work *Feminism and Geography: The Limits of Geographical Knowledge* (1993). Rose demonstrates how women occupy the paradoxically simultaneous state of being both "prison-

ers and exiles” in the grip of masculinist territory and how this in-between state equips them with the ability to imagine and stage resistance. Elaborating further, Rose states how this space “allows the subject of feminism to occupy both the centre and the margin, the inside and the outside. It is a geography structured by the dynamic tension between the poles, and it is also a multi-dimensional geography structured by the simultaneous contradictory diversity of social relations” (1993, 155). The realisation of this analogous relationship provides feminist geography with newer ways of resisting the grip of hegemonic spatialities. That is, the realisation of the map and its textuality thus has double-edged implications and the installations are thus both a roadmap as well as a warning sign for those who deal with cartographic texts and practices in some way. Most importantly, it converts the “writerly, closed text” that Barthes mentions into a “readerly text” (1977) where the very act of engaging in an alternate reading of the cartographic text undoes its assumed power and authority. At the same time, it is also a reinforcement of the text’s nature of being a self-generating feedback mechanism, where the very superimposition of the cartographic text onto the surface of game boards automatically opens several ways of engaging with the text, each way different from the other in its entry, exit and/or movement across the board that holds the text in place but also allows one to go beyond it through “an intellectual play of the hand”. Even without the involvement of the viewer’s

direct engagement, this very arrangement has its own internal logic in constant operation, with the placement of the cartographic text onto the game board's surface ensuring that the "text plays by itself" too in its very literal engagement with another text. The assumption of a map being a self-contained thing by itself is thus refused through its extremely involved engagement with other materials in a varying range of proximity and functionality, reminding one of Cubitt's (1998) remark on how "the whiteness of white sheets, has been a lure for doggerel, commentary, digression and refusal". Chowdhry thus envisions a radical way of claiming agency from hegemonic spatialities by attuning ourselves to the many ways in which the inextricable "textual condition" also ensures that the same textuality provides exit points and sites for play and transgression.

The "Thingness of the Cartographic Text"

Similarly, in considering texts as self-generating mechanisms, one also needs to consider the poetics of each major material choice in conferring something of significance to the installation. In evoking a skin-like texture not only does the installation create an affective space for the audience, but it also underscores the similar qualities that the texture of the skin in acting as a phantom substrate in this case shares with what is usually a page made of paper, thus emphasising on the importance of considering the affective and tactile aspects of textuality.

The same can be said of the usage of bodily line-like extension, that is, hair in all its many diverse existences used to create the political lines on the map. Weighing in then on the symbolic importance of the constituent elements of the installation, one anticipates a certain operational functionality that drives its constant state of “becoming”. This state of becoming then ties in not just with the concept of processual intertextuality but also finds illuminating insights from Bill Brown’s thing theory (2001) and textual materialism (2010) which urge the deeper study of constituent materials that convert a “thing” without function to an “object of value”. Like textual materialism, thing theory as a mode of critical analysis also emphasises the state of “physical materiality” in general but instead of focussing on how the constituent elements or physical properties contribute to the politics of signification, it zooms in on how the aspect of “functionality” of matter (which in this case, is the physical embodied text) changes or influences its value in human-object relations. Observing how objects are considered so by virtue of their productive value, thing theory studies representations and the process by which productive “objects of value” become “things” of affect and/or sentiment when they lose their functionality. In considering the commingling of thing theory with affect studies, Tania Rossetto, inspired by the likes of Bill Brown, and Graham Harman, (pioneering scholar of object-oriented ontology), approaches maps as objects in her work *Object-Oriented Cartography: Maps as Things* and

makes the following observations:

We saw, Harman seemed to consider cartography as a form of knowledge. His object-oriented theory privileges aesthetic, metaphorical, indirect cognition as a wiser means to access the reality of things compared with literal knowledge. While the point of knowledge is to grasp the features of reality, the point of art is to ‘experience the unknowable uniqueness of a real object’ (Harman 2018, p. 170). Aesthetics, Harman noted, is not knowledge, but a form of cognition, an indirect allusion to the real: a type of counter-knowledge. I contend that cartographic objects are not only a matter of knowledge but may also be a matter of aesthetic experience, as configured by OOO [Object Oriented Ontology]. As per Harman, there is no way to tell in literal terms the ‘insideness’ of objects, then I would add that there is no way to tell in literal term what a cartographic object is, hence the need for aesthetic counter methods to allude to the being of maps. (Rossetto 2019, 26)

In the light of Rossetto’s observations, one realises that through this enhancement of the textuality and aesthetics of the cartographic text, Chowdhry resorts to a necessary defamiliarisation to be able to go beyond the spatial confines that also chain our approaches towards reading the map and viewing it as a textual object. What is furthermore important to note is that these cartographic texts in the installations are not “functional” in their conventional sense, as in their torn, blown-out,

ripped state one can only make out barely enough to simply register only the basics. So, though Chowdhry resorts to several tactics to underscore the textual nature of the map, the cartographic text and its state of fully operational textuality thus are always only alluded to, with the actual value it serves being visible in its materiality, its “thingness”. So even as she highlights the several ways one can engage in a subversive encounter with the cartographic text, she also ensures that what is usually thought of as the “complete, self-enclosed map” is also beyond reach, as to evoke the conventional map in its entirety is to ensure the kickstarting of a usual network of intertexts, all reinforcing each other in their hegemonic domination of spatiality. Hence even though there is a memorialisation of history through the invocation of the partition through an emphasised border on the surface of the cartographic text, its defamiliarised presence ensures that what was hitherto unknown comes into being through the unknowable uniqueness of this current state.

One can take recourse to the installation titled *The Master's Tongues: Dialectics of Language* (2009) to testify to the fact that thing theory is truly capable of providing a deeper insight into the workings of textuality, even though thing theory deals more with the material substrate on which the text manifests itself upon, thus coupling thing theory and textual materialism. This exhibition is an investigation of the use of English as a tool for the expan-

sion of the colonial empire, reflecting on how the same also provided the colonised with an entry so as to speak back to the colonial masters.

Figure 8. The Masters' Tongues.

©Pritika Chowdhry, 2009

Seventy-nine tongues cast in iron make up the installation, representing the fifty-four Commonwealth countries that were once colonised by the British and the twenty-five territories that still happen to be under British governance, with the cast iron tongues being allowed to rust for over months. Chowdhry's choice of metal, as she states, has to do with the fact that iron played an important role in the Industrial Revolution of Britain, thus making it one of the major tools for exerting colonial power and influence over other countries. Here too then she resorts to finding value in what conventionally reduces an object's status to a mere thing owing to the loss of its usual functionality, as was the case with

the “deformed” or shall we say, improvised cartographic text in the other installations. In portraying language in all of its rich textual presence as the physically visible, material shape of cast-iron tongues allowed to rust, Chowdhry makes visible what is usually only grasped mentally: the “material” consequences of linguistic and textually engaged social acts which too in their shedding of certain functions and roles, play invisible roles that are intelligible only when approached with the right sensibility. In the same manner in which iron rusts with or without the “intelligible” interference of human action, we can gather that texts by themselves as self-generating feedback mechanisms, gain newer modes of being simply by their very existence, bolstered all the more by the material substrate’s very active engagement with its surrounding environment. These realisations are important in how they also generate newer ways of comprehending our way of engaging and dealing with these very significant objects which though they gain some layer of meaning by human cognition, also contain an internal circuit of meaning which can help us better read things beyond our usual way of dealing with everything. While one might say that thing theory by itself provides no such insight into realistic cartographic processes and practice, it is a misplaced assumption in truth: for it is truly in finding a newer way of seeing and reading things that we can anticipate a diversion from the hegemonic dominion of current spatial realities. Through these diverse engagements with the cartographic text, Chow-

dhry stretches the limits of the current ways of viewing, reading and engaging with maps, each viewer's situated state of knowledge an embodiment generating newer permutations and combinations of meaning-making.

Conclusion

In a nutshell, what is visible is that the newer strands of post-representational and radical geographies have a lot to gain from considering maps and the cartographic process from alternative perspectives— take for example, textual materialism and thing theory— schools of thought that are not engaged with on an everyday level in critical cartographic thinking, owing to their apparently “non-political” and hence, non-anthropomorphic approach to the world of objects and their embeddedness in the material world. But that is far from the truth, as to truly attempt the ‘radical’ or “think radical” requires one to also renew and revisit the foundational core of our basis of thinking, which is what these schools of thought will be extremely helpful in, despite it being impossible to truly escape the clutches of correlationism. Chowdhry through her *Partition Anti-Memorial Project* achieves exactly that, providing one with an artistic model or a prototype for reintroducing affect to the cartographic text by reconfiguring its physical, material constitution, thus improvising and defamiliarising that which is vital to the cartographic process and its meaning-making, assuring that the message is not a throwaway or an addi-

tional layer that is dismissible or erasable from which one recovers the ur-text, but one that is constitutive of what holds the very text in place: that is, the humble, oft-ignored substrate.

Works Cited

- Barthes, Roland. 1986. *The Rustle of Language*. Translated by Richard Howard. New York: Hill and Wang.
- Brown, Bill. 2001. "Thing Theory." *Critical Inquiry* 28 (1): 1–22. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1344258>.
- . 2010. "Introduction: Textual Materialism." *PMLA* 125 (1): 24–28. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25614434>.
- Chughtai, Ismat. 2006. *The Crooked Line*. New York: The Feminist Press at CUNY.
- Cooper, David, and Gary Priestnall. 2011. "The Processual Intertextuality of Literary Cartographies: Critical and Digital Practices." *The Cartographic Journal* 48 (4): 250–62. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1743277411Y.0000000025>.
- Cubitt, Sean. n.d. "The Materiality of the Text." Accessed April 27, 2024. <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/slade/digita/materiality.html>.
- Gordon, Avery. 1997. *Ghostly Matters: Haunting and the Sociological Imagination*. Minneapolis: U of Minnesota Press.

- Harley, J B. 1989. "DECONSTRUCTING THE MAP." *Cartographica: The International Journal for Geographic Information and Geovisualization* 26 (2): 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3138/E635-7827-1757-9T53>.
- McGann, Jerome J. 1991. *The Textual Condition*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Micieli-Voutsinas, Jacque. 2013. "'Subaltern' Remembrances: Mapping Affective Approaches to Partition Memory." *Social Transformations: Journal of the Global South* 1 (1): 27–58. <https://doi.org/10.13185/ST2013.01103>.
- Mills, Christina. 2009. "Materiality as the Basis for the Aesthetic Experience in Contemporary Art." *Graduate Student Theses, Dissertations, & Professional Papers*, January. <https://scholarworks.umt.edu/etd/1289>.
- "Partition and the Radcliffe Line." n.d. Pritika Chowdhry Art. Accessed April 27, 2024. <https://www.pritikachowdhry.com/cracking-india>.
- "Partition of India | Anti-Memorials." n.d. Pritika Chowdhry Art. Accessed April 27, 2024. <https://www.pritikachowdhry.com/partition-india-art>.
- "Remembering the Crooked Line | Partition Art." n.d. Pritika Chowdhry Art. Accessed April 27, 2024.

<https://www.pritikachowdhry.com/remembering-the-crooked-line>.

Rose, Gillian. (1991) 1993. *Feminism and Geography: The Limits of Geographical Knowledge*. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons.

Rossetto, Tania. 2019. *Object-Oriented Cartography: Maps as Things*. New York: Routledge.

Sidhwa, Bapsi. (1988) 1991. *Cracking India*. Minneapolis: Milkweed Editions.